

BRIEFING NOTE

Assessment of Geodetic Infrastructure and Human Capacity in Africa

5 June 2026

PURPOSE

This briefing note summarises the findings of the first continental assessment of geodetic infrastructure and human capacity across Africa. It is intended to inform national and continental investment decisions and to support the development of strategic plans for sustainable geodetic systems.

BACKGROUND

Geodesy underpins national mapping, land administration, disaster risk management, climate monitoring, and infrastructure development. Despite its foundational role, Africa's geodetic capacity remains fragmented and under-resourced. The UK Research and Innovation (UKRI)-funded project "Building the Foundation for Geodetic Excellence in Africa" was established to address this gap. The assessment drew on questionnaires (46 respondents from 22 countries on infrastructure; 30 respondents from 16 countries on human capacity), site visits, and a desktop review.

KEY FINDINGS

Infrastructure:

- **GNSS networks:** 48 countries have Continuously Operating Reference Stations (CORS); data are lacking for 6 countries. Approximately 91% are government-owned; 64% provide free public services.
- **Advanced space geodesy:** Africa has only one functional VLBI station and one Lunar Laser Ranging station, both in South Africa. A second VLBI station in Nigeria is expected to be operational in 2026. Only three countries participate in the global DORIS network.
- **Reference frames:** Most countries are transitioning from legacy local reference frames to modern GNSS-compatible systems aligned with the International Terrestrial Reference Frame (ITRF). WGS 84 is widely used across Central, West, and North Africa.

Human capacity:

- **Education:** Training is available across Africa but concentrated at the bachelor's degree level; specialist and postgraduate provision is limited.
- **Skills self-assessment:** ~65% of respondents rate their competency in data analysis and geodetic tools as above average.
- **Training needs:** Critical gaps in GNSS network design, installation, operation and maintenance; geodetic reference frames; and geoid modelling.

POLICY IMPLICATIONS

- Africa is **significantly underrepresented** in global space geodesy networks (VLBI, DORIS, SLR), limiting the continent's contribution to international Earth observation systems that underpin the UN Sustainable Development Goals and the UN Global Geodetic Reference Frame Resolution.
- Fragmented reference frames increase costs and reduce interoperability for cross-border infrastructure, land tenure, and disaster response programmes.
- Reliance on bachelor-level training without adequate postgraduate pathways constrains the specialist pipeline needed to operate, maintain, and sustainably expand infrastructure.

RECOMMENDED ACTIONS

1. **Invest in GNSS infrastructure.** Prioritise national investment to expand and sustain CORS networks, particularly in data-sparse regions, and ensure free access to public data.
2. **Expand advanced geodetic techniques.** Support development or upgrade of VLBI, DORIS, and SLR facilities to fulfil UN GGRF commitments and improve Africa's contribution to global geodetic data.
3. **Develop specialist human capacity.** Fund postgraduate training programmes and regional centres of excellence to address critical skills gaps in GNSS operations, reference frames, and geoid modelling.
4. **Harmonise reference frames.** Establish a harmonised, ITRF-aligned continental reference frame to reduce duplication, cut costs, and improve interoperability across national boundaries.
5. **Embed geodesy in development planning.** Integrate geodesy into national spatial data infrastructure (NSDI) strategies and continental frameworks such as the AU Agenda 2063.